

PILOT INTERVIEW RESULTS AND REFLEXIVITY

**The participant's name for the pilot run is presented using the pseudonym.*

Interview	Result and Reflexivity
<p>Participants: Diana</p> <p>Duration: 1 h 22 m</p>	<p>Diana has worked as a journalist for 12 years, and she currently serves as an editor in a news website established in 2000 by one of major and conglomerate news organizations in Indonesia. She leads a team of contributors who resides in many provinces in Indonesia. Although she is dealing with journalists from different cultures and genders, talking about identity with her is rather challenging. Diana grew up and was raised in a family that values Minang custom. Minang is an ethnic group that resides in West Sumatra, Indonesia. It is the only matrilineal society in Indonesia and the largest in the world, which believes that women and men play equally important roles in the community. Therefore, Diana believes that gender inequality is not a prevalent problem as she never experiences gender pressure in her family. She believes that women and men have the same opportunities to achieve the desired outcome in life as long as they are capable and possess the required skills regardless of gender. She also believes that she has never been in a position where her gender hinders her from achieving a better position in the workplace and that the company fairly judges her competence. She also did not notice any discrimination at work because a woman leads her newsroom, and many other women are in decision-making positions at her organization. However, she did not think that the phenomenon would result from changes brought by women to the organization. Instead, the company is always a true capitalist company that values merit over gender.</p> <p>With such conviction, the researcher should create a more flexible interview question to dig deeper into her experiences in exercising her identity. A lot of time, Diana did not realize that what she experienced was the result of gender implicit bias. For example, in her previous company, her male boss was not sensitive to her needs as a breastfeeding mom. However, she thought that the treatment happened not because of discrimination against women but because the boss was single and did not know how women worked. Therefore, giving her a straightforward question of how her gender identity hinders her work will not sit well for her.</p> <p>Moreover, from the interview, I found that it may be difficult for Indonesian women participants to answer questions on how she identifies themselves. Although Diana grew up in a matrilineal family, she spends her education and works in a big city like Jakarta with a different culture that is more patriarchal. Therefore, although she believes women and men should be equal, she somehow internalizes unfair gender expectations of women. She expresses that she is uncomfortable talking about herself, for women are expected to be humble. Therefore, general interview questions should be changed to a more contextual questions like, what kind of mother are you, what kind of journalist are you, or what your personality is like. She also believes in the expectation that women are good in detail. Therefore, she strongly believes that women are an asset for a company to create good quality products to benefit the media business.</p>

	<p>During the interview, I also noticed a form of identity that I did not consider when I designed the interview questions: the respondent's domestic identity as a mother and wife. Being a mother and wife add different experiences to their multidimensionality aspect. She suggested that being a mother influenced her decision in creating journalistic products or managing reporters. She said that she would treat a fellow mother journalist differently as she knows how it is like to be a mother and journalist. So, she does not put much pressure on deadlines on them compared to male journalists.</p>
<p>Participant: Alisa</p> <p>Duration: 1 h 34 m</p>	<p>Alisa works as an editor in an online news website with around seven years of journalistic experience. Although Alisa has the same gender as Diana, they possess significantly different identities and experiences. Alisa grew up and was raised in a family with a strong Betawi custom. Compared to Minang, Betawi is an ethnic group native to the city of Jakarta who holds patriarchal values and often strongly emphasizes their Islamic identity. At the same time, she is a wife of a U.S. citizen who has a different culture and comes from a country where gender equality and diversity are highly discussed. Her background allows her to have high sensitivity and awareness to gender inequality and diversity issues at work. She noticed that no women hold top-level management in her company, which she figured because of the male-oriented organizational culture. She has also identified some gender discrimination she experienced at work. From the interview, the researcher learned that cultural identity should be accentuated in the interview as it significantly influences participants' worldviews and illuminates intersectionality issues.</p>